

United Nations
Educational, Scientific and
Cultural Organization

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ICT for Development
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Guidance Note

Introduction

From the Report: Education for the most marginalised post-COVID-19: Guidance for governments on the use of digital technologies in education
ACT THREE (OF THREE): GUIDANCE NOTES

Date November 2020

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EdTech Hub

Clear evidence, better decisions, more learning.

Report homepage <https://edtechhub.org/education-for-the-most-marginalised-post-covid-19/>

Guidance Notes

This final Act of this Report includes *14 Guidance Notes* that provide focused advice for governments on some of the most important specific issues where effective and appropriate interventions using digital technologies can help significantly to increase equity and resilience in education systems.¹ These are largely based on the suggestions of those involved in our consultations, and are an integral part of this Report. However, they can also be used separately by stakeholders who would like guidance on the most important actions that must be undertaken and delivered. Each of them contains an introductory contextual section followed by relevant guidance in a boxed format that can be adapted in whatever ways are most relevant. They can, for example, be used to craft infographics or slide decks (see *Annex 4*), turned into posters, or simply used as reminders pinned above a desk. Much of this guidance is in the form of ‘what needs to be done’. Given the emphasis of the Report that context matters and there is no such thing as ‘one size fits all’, these recommendations also usually do not suggest precisely how governments should go about doing them. It would be presumptuous to do so. Instead, each guidance note also includes examples of how they have been achieved elsewhere (including things that should *not* be done), and a short selection of further reading that can provide suggestions for ways through which others have thought about or tried to achieve these outcomes.

The *Guidance Notes* are grouped into five main clusters (listed in alphabetical order):

Content

- In the local context — using digital technologies to develop local content.
- Sharing Open Educational Resources (OER) with Creative Commons (CC) open licenses.

Including the poorest and most marginalised

- Digital technologies and girls’ education.
- Inclusion and accessible learning for people with disabilities.
- Supporting the effective use of digital technologies for learning by refugees and displaced persons.
- Digital technologies and education in Small Island Developing States (SIDS).

Infrastructural issues

- Ensuring resilient connectivity.
- Resilient and sustainable energy solutions.

Pedagogies

- Involving marginalised young people in the design of their own education.
- Prioritising effective and appropriate teacher training.
- Using digital technologies effectively in support of vocational learning and training.

¹ Further guidance notes will be developed and shared in due course in response to demand and our continuing work on these issues. These updates and additions will be made available on our site at <https://ict4d.org.uk/technology-and-education-post-covid-19/>.

Learning safely and effectively together

- Ensuring rigorous monitoring and evaluation of initiatives using digital technologies in education for the most marginalised.
- Ensuring that children are safe when using digital technologies for learning.
- Partnerships with the private sector and civil society.

All of the *Guidance Notes* are to some extent cross-cutting, reflecting the holistic framing of this Report. However, they are usually of most relevance to one of the main core themes of this Report as indicate below:

Guidance Notes	The five core themes of Part 2 of the Report				
	<i>Whole society approach</i>	<i>Enabling access</i>	<i>Context specific</i>	<i>Appropriate pedagogies</i>	<i>Wise use of technology</i>
Content					
Contextualised content	●		●	●	
OER			●	●	●
Including the poorest and most marginalised					
Girls' education			●	●	●
People with disabilities			●	●	●
Refugees			●	●	●
SIDS		●	●	●	●
Infrastructural issues					
Resilient connectivity	●	●	●		●
Sustainable energy		●	●		
Pedagogies					
Learners voices	●			●	●
Teacher training			●	●	●
Vocational training	●		●	●	
Learning safely and effectively together					
Monitoring and evaluation	●	●	●	●	●
Digital safety	●		●	●	●
Partnerships	●		●	●	●

● Of most relevance

● Highly relevant

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Publication typesetting by User Design,
Illustration and Typesetting
www.userdesignillustrationandtypesetting.com